

TG-DATA AR6 TO AR7 TRANSITION

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Summary

This document was developed to reflect the experience of the Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments (TG-Data) during the IPCC AR6 cycle and thereby provide some guidance and recommendations for the incoming TG-Data group formed during the selection of authors for AR7. The document is structured around TG-Data purposes as defined in their Terms of Reference. The document reflects the experience of TG-Data members, including data officers from Technical Support Units of the three Working Groups for AR6 and AR7.

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1. Introduction

According to TG-Data Terms of Reference¹ (TOR), membership is tied to the assessment cycle of the IPCC, and is updated at the latest with the author selection process of working groups of the assessment reports (AR). Based on these procedures, it is expected that TG-Data membership is renewed during 2025 with the AR nomination process commencing immediately after the AR7 report outlines are discussed and approved during P-62. The objective of this document is to provide insights and reflections from current TG-Data members on the AR6 experience, and smooth the transition into AR7.

The TG-Data membership update occurs at a time when the Data Distribution Centre (DDC) faces multiple challenges. This document describes the expected responsibilities of the DDC in the AR7 cycle, TG-Data' role in ensuring DDC has adequate resources, and the need for coordination between DDC and Technical Support Units (TSU).

The TG-Data Transition document is organised around TG-Data roles and responsibilities as described in TG-Data TOR. For each one of them, we comment on both past achievements and recommendations for potential improvements. At the end of this document, we also provide general insights about current experience during AR6, and operational recommendations for AR7. This document complements the TG-Data AR7 Recommendation document presented at 65th Session of the IPCC Bureau as Appendix 1 to Document BUR-LX/INF.2. More general information on TG-Data can be found in the TG-Data webpage².

2. TG-Data purpose

According to TG-Data ToR the purpose of the TG-Data is to:

- 1.1 Provide guidance to the IPCC's Data Distribution Centre (DDC) in order to provide curation, transparency, traceability and stability of data and scenarios related to the reports of the IPCC.
- 1.2 Facilitate, in cooperation with the DDC, the availability and consistent use of climate change related data and scenarios in support of the implementation of the work programme of the IPCC.
- 1.3 Facilitate in cooperation with the DDC the availability and use of climate change related data resulting from the activities of the IPCC in accordance with the mandate of the IPCC.

3. Achievements and recommendations regarding TG-Data roles and responsibilities

The focus of TG-Data activities evolved throughout the AR6 cycle. Work started with the preparation of guidelines for FAIR data within IPCC, and their joint implementation by TSUs and the DDCs. This process has demanded an important effort and dedication from the DDCs, TSUs and report authors to prepare, clean and document different types of data (input, intermediate and final). With the publication of the reports, attention shifted to outreach, providing training to the practitioner and research community on the use of IPCC related products (e.g. WGI Interactive Atlas and the IIASA Scenario Explorer). Below we present a recount of achievements and suggest recommendations for each of TG-Data's roles and responsibilities.

1 https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2020/10/TG-Data_TORs.pdf.

2 <https://www.ipcc.ch/data/>.

3.1. Provide oversight of the DDC's activities, in close liaison with the three IPCC Working Group Bureaus (WGBs)

Achievements

- TG-Data co-chairs held monthly meetings with DDC managers to coordinate activities, facilitate collaboration with TSUs and plan resources;
- Bureau and Panel reports systematically include sections describing DDC data holdings and catalog statistics;

Recommendations

- Ensure WG Co-Chairs are aware of relevant activities within DDCs, either through TSU representatives or meetings with TG-Data Co-Chairs;
- Updating the DDC MoU as the DDC structure evolves during AR7;

3.2. Identify in close liaison with the Co-Chairs or their representatives of the three Working Groups (WGs) relevant external sources of data, scenario information, and external data partnerships

Achievements

TG-Data helped materialise different external partnerships during AR6. The following lists actions taken jointly with partner organizations related to data access and best practices in open science.

- Review WGI Interactive Atlas FAIR practices³;
- Work with WCRP WGCM to license CMIP6 model outputs under CC-BY-4.0;
- Work with IIASA to develop outreach material for its Scenarios Explorer;
- Work with WGI CLAs to organize WGI Atlas outreach activities;
- Advance the concept of “complex citations” in collaboration with the Research Data Alliance (RDA);

Recommendations

- In collaboration with WG Co-Chairs, participate in discussions with data providers to facilitate author access to data and metadata with proper licensing, versioning and crediting information allowing reuse. For example:
 - Liaise with relevant processes/institutions e.g. WCRP CMIP and CORDEX and have an IPCC TG-Data representative in the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP);
 - Establish partnerships with WGIII relevant institutions (e.g. IEA)
 - Establish new partnerships with earth observation data providers (e.g. NASA, ESA and JAXA) to support authors from regions with sparse measurement networks;
 - Establish links with broadscale surface, near surface and oceanic observations networks (e.g. AGAGE, NOAA, CSIRO, ICOS);
 - Consider engagement through the WMO Greenhouse Gases and Related Tracers Measurement Techniques (GGMT) meeting and the [G3W project](#)⁴;
 - Consider reaching out to the Global Climate Observing System to discuss plans for “climate data centers” and potential synergies with IPCC activities;

³ Iturbide, M., Fernández, J., Gutiérrez, J.M. et al. Implementation of FAIR principles in the IPCC: the WGI AR6 Atlas repository. *Sci Data* 9, 629 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01739-y>

⁴ <https://wmo.int/activities/global-greenhouse-gas-watch-g3w>

- Strengthen collaboration with institutions advancing best practices in Open Science, such as:
 - The Technical Support Unit for Knowledge and Data of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES);
 - National Assessments (e.g. USA, Japan, EEA);
 - The Research Data Alliance, whose work on complex citations is highly relevant to IPCC data traceability and credit assignment to external data providers;

3.3. Provide in close liaison with the Co-Chairs or their representatives of three WGs guidance to incorporate consistently and efficiently relevant regional data and scenario information into the IPCC assessment work by developing and proposing policies and structures that will help to link and curate data as needed and used by the Co-Chairs or their representatives of the three WGs

Achievements

- Development of a key document that guided the process on how to make the IPCC assessment process FAIR ([FAIR guidelines](#)⁵);
- Information on the provenance of the figures provided by the authors through the TSU was used by the DDC at DKRZ to document for individual CMIP6 datasets the connections to the final/figure data, the code and the AR6 figure page. This information will be published as ComplexCitation pilot using Zenodo enabling DDC at CEDA to refer to this provenance information⁶.

Recommendations

- Given the evolving nature of open science and FAIR principle implementation we recommend a constant review and update of the FAIR Guidelines document and improved integration into IPCC procedures, e.g. such as in reporting potential data error issues through the Error Protocol process;
- We recommend an early engagement with scenarios development community (IAMC, etc) on the guidance on use of new scenarios in the AR7 cycle;
- We recommend an early engagement with the city climate change research community, such as Urban Climate Change Research Network (UCCRN), on collaboration of input data and applications development in the AR7 cycle, especially SRCities;
- We recommend to implement the RDA Complex Citation recommendations⁷ into the AR7; the Complex Citation implementation into AR7 is ongoing work at the moment of finishing this document⁸].

3.4. Recommend partnerships with external organisations to ensure the stability of the IPCC data sets they hold

Achievements

- In case of CMIP6, the IPCC DDC ensured long-term preservation of the subset of CMIP6 used within AR6 WGI, as agreed in the WCRP WIP as white paper⁹;

5 <https://zenodo.org/records/6504469>

6 See <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/15AruKRX1FcQvs6yBhgBP-60q1kLHiND0/edit#slide=id.p6>.

7 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14106602>

8 Concept: : https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Dnm4MATOI0gbHmb9Rx2wGgZp_dstDF1Z5fQBjBh_1Uk;

Meetings/Coordination: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SMBDWm41-AwU6WCm7QbiD4pWL1Dk8e3_KJ7x56ZcF5U

9 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.35178>

- Long-term preservation of CORDEX data subset included in the WGI Interactive Atlas;
- Implementation of the FAIR principles for a subset of final figures. In Figure 1 we present the final accomplishment in terms of figures that were included in the process.

Recommendations

- Identify a DDC partner to take over responsibilities previously held by DKRZ to curate and archive CMIP climate model outputs and the planned archival of the data underpinning the WGI Interactive Atlas;
- Extend the curation of final figures to a large fraction of figures generated by AR7.

Figure 1. Data availability per report and chapter. Each square stands for a graphic, and is colored gray if it is conceptual, blue if its underlying data is available at the DDC, and white if it's not linked to a data source. Note that additional data was added for the SYR report following AR6 through a rescue effort.

3.5. Provide expert information on data and scenarios in support of the implementation of the work programme of the IPCC

Achievements

- Elaboration of FAIR Guidelines¹⁰ and their implementation (see Appendix 1);
- Elaboration of [Licence guidelines](#)¹¹;
- Publication of software¹² for the production of many IPCC WGI AR6 final figures;
- Represented data publication practice in the IPCC Informal Group on Publications and Translations (IGPubs)

Recommendations

- Recommendations for AR7 regarding the life cycle management of reports' figures and associated artifacts (data and software) have been initiated by the TG-Data and the TSUs. These include guidelines for figures produced programmatically through scripts (and managed via a GitHub repository) as well as those generated using standard software, such as Excel or similar tools;
- The Data management workflow draft, documented in Figure 2, shows the ideal high level process that should be implemented for the final release of the reports. We recommend that all report drafts follow this workflow, allowing for reduced metadata details initially, provided all artifacts are included;
- The workflow may be refined in collaboration with TSU-DDC-TG-Data, also depending on the Figure and Metadata Management tools that will be made available to authors later in the cycle.

Figure 2. Draft data management workflows for AR7. Panel (a) describes the recommended workflow for working data and code, panel (b) for input data and code, and panel (c) for final data and code

10 <https://zenodo.org/records/6504469>

11 <https://zenodo.org/records/7431834>

12 <https://github.com/IPCC-WG1>

3.6. In cooperation with the co-chairs or their representatives of the three WGs, develop and update good practice guidance materials related to data and scenarios, targeting IPCC authors who lack familiarity with the IPCC process and/or the relevant data and scenarios

Achievements

- We developed workshops with authors to explain tools like ESMValTool and the WGI Atlas and also explain the procedures of FAIR implementation¹³;
- TG-Data members interacted with authors starting with WGI LAM3 and WGII LAM3, then participated in a virtual session of WGIII LAMs afterwards.

Recommendations

- Focus outreach and training activities for authors in the form of workshops and webinars, complemented by regularly updated training materials that are made publicly accessible for reference; Special attention should be given to WGII and WGIII
- Start interactions in LAM1 to show to authors the objectives and principles of FAIR implementation in IPCC¹⁴. At LAM2 TSU could organize an author workshop and between FOD and SOD (during the Expert Review process) more frequent author virtual training sessions could be organized;
- TG-Data has initiated the development of training material on FAIR practices for managing data, software and figures throughout the IPCC reports lifecycle. The tutorial is collaboratively developed using a dedicated GitHub repository¹⁵, compiled, and made accessible online, ensuring authors have easy access to these resources. We recommend sustaining and further refining the material through the new task group, working in close collaboration with the TSUs.

3.7. Contribute to building capacity in the use of data and scenarios for climate-related research, particularly in developing and transition-economy regions and countries. e.g. through encouraging activities such as expert meetings and liaison with relevant academic institutions to address the requirements of developing countries. To achieve this, TG-DATA may work with organisations and activities that have training as their core mandate but would not develop training programmes on their own

Achievements

- TG-Data prepared a dedicated web page which included description of TG-Data, membership, activities and links to guidance documents, data and outreach activities of IPCC products: <https://www.ipcc.ch/data/>
- Elaboration of the DDC data catalogue
- TG-Data prepared two Expert Meeting proposals, one on Probabilistic Risk Assessments of Climate Hazards ([IPCC-LX/Doc. 11](#)), and another on Earth Observation data accessibility for climate studies ([IPCC-LXI/INF. 7](#)) the latter is still under consideration.
- TG-Data work was presented at the following conferences and meetings:
 - International Data Week 2023 (IDW23), Salzburg, Austria, 23-26 October 2023 (Session Data Linking / Knowledge Graphs): Stockhause, M., Pirani, A., Sitz, L., Krüss, B., Pascoe, C., MacRae, M., Anderson, E., & Fisher, E. (2023, October 25). Implementation of the IPCC FAIR Guidelines into the Sixth Assessment Report (AR6): benefit, challenges and recommendations for AR7. International Data Week 2023 (IDW23), Salzburg, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10039597>

¹³ <https://www.ipcc.ch/event/wgi-training-on-data-and-software-development/>

¹⁴ For SRCities LAM1 TSU-DDC-TG-Data developed the data curation section of the Author's Handbook, which was presented to all authors.

¹⁵ <https://github.com/IPCC-AR7/ipcc-author-guidance>

- o EGU 2023: Open Science and Data Help Desk: Stockhouse, M., Sitz, L., Pascoe, C., Pirani, A., Anderson, E., Cammarano, D., & MacRae, M. (2023). IPCC FAIR data approach. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825876>
- o [EGU 2024: Open Science and Data Help Desk](#): Stockhouse, M., Pascoe, C., Sitz, L., & Pirani, A. (2024). IPCC FAIR data approach. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10821975>
- o AGU 2024, Washington DC, 9-13 December, Oral Sessions and Poster Sessions (Xiaoshi, Martina, David M, Charlotte P., Molly MacRae)
AGU 2024, Washington DC, 9-13 December, Oral Sessions and Poster Sessions (Xiaoshi, Martina, David M, Charlotte P., Molly MacRae)
Using Complex Citations to Close the Provenance Gap Between IPCC AR6 Figures and CMIP6 Simulations, C Pascoe et al. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14605443>
Implementing FAIR Data Principles in the IPCC AR6 WGI Report, C. Pascoe et al. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14605539>
Benefit and limitations of the application of the TRUST principles on the jointly managed IPCC Data Distribution Centre, M. Stockhouse et al. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14626702>
Collaborations across boundaries in the Data Distribution Center (DDC) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to support climate assessments and interdisciplinary applications, X. Xing et al.
Building a FAIR Foundation: Managing The IPCC Data Distribution Center (DDC) Catalogue, A. Milward et al.
- TG-Data together with WGI prepared three regional outreach activities linked to the outcomes of the Working Group I report that was released in 2021¹⁶. The objectives of these activities were to:
 - o Present the main results of the WGI report;
 - o Engage with the regional research practitioner community over specific regional domains;
 - o Present the data availability with special emphasis on the Interactive Atlas (IA) providing regional information and synthesis (from the Technical Summary and the regional chapters 10-11-12-Atlas Chapters).
- TG-Data together with WGIII prepared five regional outreach activities linked to the outcomes of the Working Group III report that was released in 2022¹⁷. The objectives of these activities were to:
 - o Present the main results of the WGIII contribution to the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report;
 - o Engage with the regional research practitioner community over specific regional domains;
 - o Present the data availability with special emphasis on the AR6 Scenarios Database and Scenario Explorer providing regional information and synthesis.

Recommendations

- In the case interactive products are produced in AR7, we recommend to prepare outreach activities related to these products prior to the final report publication date. This implies early engagement with potential authors willing to participate and also external regional partners willing to host the activities;
- Continue to present TG-Data and DDC work at major relevant data conferences and meetings and those IPCC authors and agencies are involved with, such as International Data Week (IDW), UN World Data Forum (UNDWF), EGU/AGU;
- Expand the nature of outreach and training activities with a focus on researchers in developing countries (aside from authors) in the principles and tools used for FAIR implementation in the form of workshops and webinars;

¹⁶ <https://www.ipcc.ch/event/interactive-atlas-regional-webinars/>.

¹⁷ <https://www.ipcc.ch/event/ipcc-tg-data-scenario-database-and-scenario-explorer-webinars/>.

- In consultation with WGII Co-Chairs contribute from a data perspective on the elaboration of the revision and update of the 1994 IPCC Technical Guidelines on impacts and adaptation.

3.8. Explore in close consultation with the Co-Chairs or their representatives of the three WGs options for a sustainable structure, functioning, and resourcing for the DDC

DDC has been a key component of the data management process of IPCC since 1997¹⁸. Up until AR6, DDC were tasked with archiving key input datasets used through AR. With AR6 and the implementation of FAIR guidelines, DDCs were also asked to curate and archive final figure data. This occurred at a time when resources at their disposal to contribute to IPCC were declining or becoming less predictable. As a result, the operation of DDC services in 2024 and 2025 is sustained through direct funding from the IPCC Trust Fund. This is an interim solution, and a short term objective for 2025 is to mobilize resources to go back to a model where countries contribute DDC services to the IPCC.

Achievements

- Incorporation of new DDC members (CSIC, Metadatawork), formalised through a [Memorandum of Understanding](#)¹⁹;
- Attempts to increase funding and external collaboration to DDC were executed by TG-Data Co chairs in coordination with IPCC Secretariat. This included conversations with potential external donors and the publication of resource mobilisation letters. The outcome of this process was the financial contribution received from the government of Australia and France and the Trottier Foundation.
- The IPCC Panel at P60 approved the use of the IPCC Trust Fund to secure DDC services to the IPCC. This process is to be repeated for 2025, but should be replaced by national contributions that do not require Trust Fund support.

Recommendations

- Pursue work with IPCC Secretariat to mobilize resources for DDC;
- Support DDCs in their efforts to fund IPCC activities, making sure communications and outreach to external stakeholders are well coordinated through TG-Data;
- Make sure the process is implemented ensuring proper structure, functioning and resourcing for the DDC to:
 - Cooperate with TG-Data in facilitating the availability and consistent use of climate change related data and scenarios in support of the implementation of the work programme of the IPCC.
 - Cooperate with TG-Data in facilitating the availability and use of climate change related data resulting from the activities of the IPCC in accordance with the mandate of the IPCC.
- Make sure the process is implemented following procedures that impede conflict of interests.

¹⁸ Stockhause, M. and Lautenschlager, M.: Twenty-five years of the IPCC Data Distribution Centre at the DKRZ and the Reference Data Archive for CMIP data, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 15, 6047–6058, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-6047-2022>, 2022.

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/5914483>.

4. TG-Data mode of operation

Below is a description of how TG-Data operated during the AR6 cycle. This mode of operation should be revised and updated if necessary by the new TG-Data members.

TG-Data organised its work around different subgroups that were more or less active at different stages in the cycle:

- Executive sub-group

- Roles: Coordinate TG-Data activities; Ensure subgroups are progressing toward their own deliverables; Strengthen connection to all WGs and TSUs.

- Data prioritization sub-group

- Roles: Identify key datasets used by IPCC authors whose long term archival is not guaranteed.

- DDC subgroup

- Roles: Manage the DDC pages of the website; Liaison between TSU and DDC.

- External Partnerships Subgroup

- Roles: Create linkages with organizations sharing TG-Data goals; Identify potential new DDCs (for example in developing countries); Establish connection with organizations sharing similar objectives.

- FAIR Subgroup

- Roles: Develop cross-WG data/code curation guidelines; Develop technical guidelines for FAIR principles; Review of the success of the implementation process; Organize expert meetings; Prepare work for further steps (AR7).

- Web pages and Outreach subgroup

- Roles: Create web page content; Write guidance material; Develop training material; Organize expert meetings and training workshops; Conduct user surveys;

- Provenance / Complex Citation subgroup

- Roles: Enhance the traceability of the outputs by implementing the Complex Citation concept; Improve Author support and machine-accessibility of data workflow based on provenance records; Coordination with external tool providers and RDA Complex Citation Implementation IG ([Concept; Meeting/Coordination](#)).

We suggest using the help offered by the Secretariat to ensure subgroups have regular meetings and follow-up on action items. Incoming members are welcome to review the subgroup mission and organisation.

It is expected that TG-Data co-chairs participate at both Panel and Bureau meetings in person or virtually especially if being asked by both groups to present a progress report. Progress reports are sent to the IPCC secretariat at least one month prior to the date of the meeting. Special formats for the preparation of these reports are provided by the Secretariat.

TG-Data members are expected to participate in an annual Face to Face meeting and also in virtual teleconferences that are organised throughout the year (typically one each 3 months).

To provide potential future guidance to new TG-Data members the following list provides contact information to all TG-Data members: [List of expertise](#)²⁰. If needed salient TG-Data members are available for a meeting with new TG-Data members to help for a smooth transition.

Finally, some key documents that need to be considered in TG-Data are the following:

- [TOR](#)²¹
 - [FAIR Guidelines](#)²²
 - [License guidance](#)²³
 - [AR7 recommendation](#)²⁴
 - [TG-Data paper](#)²⁵
-

20 <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1ogjwjl1kSxqFqxeai60VLxf2TRHqe2sgr4Gw3zDyeo/edit?gid=0#gid=0> .

21 https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2020/10/TG-Data_TORs.pdf.

22 <https://zenodo.org/records/6504469>,

23 <https://zenodo.org/records/7431834>.

24 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10059281>.

25 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000533>.

Appendix 1 - Archiving of input and final datasets in AR6 cycle via TSU-DDC collaboration

An important aspect of TG-Data work is related to collaboration between the DDC, the TSU and Authors. In preparation for AR7 we provide here some insights about how this collaboration could happen based on the AR6 experience.

Archiving CMIP6 Input Data

The information of which datasets of the CMIP6 data were used in each figure was provided by the TSU of WGI per chapter (Figure 3). With this information, the archival datasets were identified, and the metadata was gathered from CMIP6 infrastructure components such as ESGF index, ES-DOC, CMIP6 Citation Service and Errata Service. The archival and curation process is documented as part of the IPCC WGI GitHub repository (<https://github.com/IPCC-WG1/DDC-AR6-CMIP6-Data-Archival>; Stockhause, M., Wachsmann, F., & Krüss, B. (2023). DDC AR6 Reference Data Archival of CMIP6 input datasets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8109876>).

After the data was archived, the information related to figure usage of the data was used to add references to the software, the final datasets and the report/figure webpages using the WGI GitHub information on software/final dataset. These connections between the different digital objects were published as a Complex Citation pilot.

Figure 3. High-level archival workflow for the CMIP6 Input data subset used in AR6 WGI.

* DataCite publication and publication on IPCC webpages

The archiving of WGI figure data

Close collaboration between the WGI TSU and CEDA enabled the publication of 226 figures from IPCC 6th Assessment Report (AR6) WGI.

It is worth noting that, except for the figures from the summary for policymakers, the archiving of figure data occurred after the report had been published. This presented its own challenges in terms of interaction with authors, but at least meant that the figure data was less likely to be in a state of flux.

Workflow (refer to Figure 4):

- TSU liaised with authors to collect information about the figure data and the figure data files.
- CEDA archived* the figure data and created a catalogue record.
- Authors reviewed the figure catalogue record.
- CEDA published the figure data and, where appropriate, issued DOIs.
- The CEDA catalogue record for the figure was mirrored on the DDC.
- The CEDA catalogue DOI was referenced from the figure page in the IPCC AR6.

A catalogue record was created by CEDA for all of the figures included in this process.

Catalogue records contained a version identifier. Updated figure datasets were issued with a new catalogue record.

Figure 4. Figure publication workflow for WGI figure data publication workflow

Where data was archived:

In some instances, data and code were blended in processing chains. A decision tree (Figure 5) was used to identify the appropriate archival location for data: Zenodo and/or the CEDA archive.

It is expected that guidance and earlier intervention with IPCC authors in AR7 will see more cases with a clearer separation of figure data from the processing chains that created them. This includes the provision of templates for the structuring of datasets and metadata.

It is hoped that clear data management instructions for authors will streamline the data publication workflow.

Figure 5. Decision tree for WGI data archival

Catalogue Architecture:

The nature of the CEDA catalogue database required there to be a one-to-one mapping between a figure catalogue record and the archived dataset (Figure 6). If a figure’s data was used again in, say, the summary for policymakers, a separate instance of the dataset was archived, and the two instances were associated with each other via a relationship descriptor.

Figure 6. Catalogue architecture for WGI figure data publication at CEDA.

Specific choices about the nature of the catalogue structure for archiving the WGI figures were made to fit within the confines of the existing catalogue schema used by CEDA. This is not a mandate, other choices could be made.

The archiving of figure data for the WGII and WGIII

The figure data publication for WGII and WGIII followed a similar methodology. Data was collected for figures in their summary for policymakers and for some figures in their technical summary.

Workflow/procedure:

WGII and WGIII figures were first created by authors and then handed to a data and graphics officer in the TSU to give them a unified look and feel. This is different to WGI where authors were generally responsible for the publication of their own figures. The WGII and WGIII TSUs worked with authors to retrieve figure data. DDC and TSUs worked together to create metadata forms. The TSU graphics officer provided figure data to the DDC (CIESIN) and/or MetadataWorks and completed a metadata form which included: title, authors, year of publication, abstract, temporal coverage, spatial coverage, data format, data volume, version and data license (license was required to be cc.by.4.0).

The DDC (CIESIN), as the data publisher, performed quality control (QA/QC) in which the uploaded data was checked vs the figures in the assessment report.

The content provided via the metadata form was used to generate a landing page for each of the datasets. The landing page was reviewed by the TSU graphics/data officers and in some cases the authors also reviewed. Once the landing page, data and metadata were approved, DDC (CIESIN) issued the DOI and published the data set.

The dataset record was then mirrored on the MetaDataWorks DDC catalogue.

The archiving of input data for the WGII

Workflow/procedure:

Certain WGII authors contact TG-Data for assistance on archiving the input data used in the chapters. DDC (CIESIN) worked with graphics/data officers to assess the data status to see if the data were archived elsewhere. If not, CIESIN contacted the data sources and worked with them on data licensing of the versions that were used in the chapters. Then CIESIN initially archived the data but without minting DOIs. The data DOIs were created and the data were made publicly available when the chapters were finalised.

The archiving of the WGII integrated databases

Workflow/procedure:

WGII graphics/data officers and DDC (CIESIN) worked together to put together three data collections/databases: IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) Climate Change Risk Assessment Database (A collection of 13 individual data sets), IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) Observed and Projected Impact Assessment Database (A collection of 29 individual data sets), and IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) Adaptation Database. The first two were successfully completed before the TSU were closed and archived at DDC (CIESIN).

AR6 Data Rescue work

After TSUs were closed, requests for access to IPCC datasets nevertheless continued. Where these datasets were not already published, the DDC (CIESIN) was advised by the AR6 TSU officers to retrieve the data from authors. The process has been ongoing. The plan is to complete datasets for all figures in the synthesis report by the end of July, 2025. The challenges include missing or lost data after the closure of the TSUs, missing data licensing agreements, version control issues, and missing quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) so that some data do not match the published figures. It costs much more time and effort to track, retrieve, archive, and resolve legal and technical issues. If DDC and TSUs work closely together from the very beginning, similar issues can be avoided in AR7.
